

The African Writer and the English Language

By

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Abstract

Renowned Nigerian writer Chinua Achebe is a novelist, poet, critic, and educator. His first great novel, *Things Fall Apart* (1958), is widely recognized as the most widely-read work of modern African literature. His paper "The African Writer and the English Language" explores several topics, including the definition of African literature, the differences between nationalized and cultural literature, and the place of English in African literature. He focuses on the linguistic problem. Is it feasible to consider literature published in languages other than English to be African? the meaning of African literature, and lastly, is it possible for a writer to work effectively in two languages, English and Spanish? Each of these questions will be explained in this review.

Key words: African literature, English language, Chinua Achebe, Nigerian writer.

The African Writer and the English Language

In his article "The African writer and the English language," Achebe finds what is known as "African literature." African literature is difficult to define since it often contains a wide range of noteworthy works. Africa is a vast continent home to numerous languages and customs. Achebe is attempting to clarify that the June 1952 gathering of African authors writing in English was ineffective since it was unable to define "African Literature" due to numerous obstacles in providing specific answers.

The term "Creative writing in which an African setting is authentically handled or to which experiences originating in Africa are integral" (Achebe, 183) was created in a later class, however Achebe is not satisfied with that description. because, in his opinion, African writing is not capable of being so obviously unique. "A grouping of connected elements ethnic and national literatures of Africa" is how he describes African literature. (Achebe, 184).

Trying to provide a response to a significant query such as: Can non-native writing be considered African literature? In a 1975 essay, Achebe predicted that individual nation-conditions on the African continent would grow and that many of those states would adopt English as their national language. According to him, the colonial languages communicated a common language among socially dispersed groups. He regrets that he probably won't be able to study even the several Nigerian languages, but he also believes that these languages will "have to enlarge as branches in order to nourish the one innermost language enjoying countrywide currency." (185).

The use of the English language as a national language has several advantages and disadvantages. In his writings, Achebe tries to caution readers from "flinging out the good quality" of English along with "the evil" (Achebe, 185). He points out that English is a universal language and that using it will have the advantage of exposing African literary works to a global audience. He makes a distinction between this and Brazilian Portuguese usage, which keeps many excellent examples of Brazilian literature from reaching a larger audience.

Obi Wali says that African writers should "acknowledge the fact that some true African literature should be printed in African languages," while Achebe rejects his assertion. He uses Casely Hayford, Christopher Okigbo, Olaudo Equiano, Amos Tutuola, and J.P. Clark as examples to show how innovative and exciting the African breakthrough in English is (Achebe, 186–187). He points out that an African writer's ability to use English like a native speaker is not necessary—in fact, it can be harmful.

A national literature is one that occupies the entire state for its district and comprehended or possible audience all the way through its terrain. However, a literature that is printed in the nationwide language. A cultural literature is obtainable simply to one racial assembly within the state. For example Nigeria, the national literature is the literature which is written in English; and the national literatures are in Hausa, Ibo, Yoruba, Efik, Edo, Ijaw, etc., etc. Any effort to define African literature in requisites which ignore the complications of the African prospect at the substance time is destined to disappointment. After the removal of colorless rule shall have been finished, the most distinct significant truth in Africa is the second half of the 20th will materialize to be the increase of individual nation- states. It seems that African literature will track the equivalent prototype.

The African continent is estranged into a great diversity of racial cultures, which exercise special languages in order to correspond and write down literature. Achebe states that these civilizations do not desire to recognize the English language as their representative communiqué and literature despite the fact that it is an intercontinental language that gives a supplementary fixed and resourceful type of announcement. To additional verification of this tip, Achebe employs the subsequent extract, "If it didn't give them a song, it gave them a tongue". Throughout this quotation Achebe is suggesting to the competence of the English language and how it extended internationality and educational variety in stating all the way through a huge part of Africa and if employed further, will in the upcoming generate a supplementary steadier message organized for all the countries surrounding different traditions during the varied continent of Africa.

The charge of a world language must be organized in order to recompense its obedience to many special types of use. At this point, Achebe is stating that the English language that is used by African authors will be special. This will be one of its forces. He states that authors have to increase an English that is comprehensible yet remarkably their individual and able to communicate their distinctive skills (Achebe, 187).

Achebe states that he has no alternative and aims to employ the language he was prearranged and has made his own. On the other hand, he anticipated that others will

maintain to write down in their native tongues consequently that African cultural literature will "increased side by side" with African nationalized literature (Achebe, 188).

Achebe's major reason was to correspond the thought that the opening of the English language by British missionaries in different components of Africa was ethnically more constructive than unenthusiastic. The opening of the English Language into the African traditions allowed them to squeeze a language used universally, which produces powerful international associations and as stated before, improves the communiqué structure. In reality, in Achebe's "Things Fall Apart", it is obvious that the preface of the English language brought by British missionaries had more pessimistic than constructive effects on the Igbo society, permitting them to combine additional and tolerate understandable look and liberty of speech.

Literature, written in an intercontinental and stable language as English language, allocates further citizens around the world to understand the text and feel associations that are unfeasible to experience with Swahili, as it is a foreign language together with this in a precise region and not spoken and any other continent all around the world. Achebe also mentions that he would be devoted to find out all the languages broaden about the continent, although it is not possible. He illuminates that the English language is one of the mainly widespread habits of communication, and binds a sturdy contact tie linking nations.

Achebe thinks that the explanation for practicing English language as resources of communiqué in his novel is that British colonialism gave the prospect for special cultural groupings in the region of Africa and on the whole to professionally be able to converse with every one. He subsequently mentions that African authors who prefers to write down their parts of literature in the English language are not un nationalistic, they are absolutely prejudiced by the fascination of the English language in the African society, and employ it to start and facilitate a superior international communiqué method.

The English language integrated groups that were sorting out, as a consequence, authorizing an improved communiqué and perceptive among them. Achebe discusses that before the imperialistic era, Africa was totally estranged by tribes and special

traditions that had special communiqué organisms. The English language recognized a representative method of announcement, permitting the traditions to aid each other extend and more produce constructive links with the intend of nationalized and intercontinental development. It too extended and eased instruction, since most African locales educated a widespread way to converse and convey.

The power of the British guided to an elevated sociopolitical alteration, counting, new-fangled political systems and additional societal association between educational groups. These modifications permitted races and tribes positioned in the similar area in order to merge into influential states that shared the equivalent political system and could convey themselves by using the English language as a widespread communiqué outline, and by creating resourceful political and societal norms that led to the construction of a cohesive and functioning nation.

Achebe gives enormous instances of African text in his essay. It is significant for all literature instructors. however particularly those instructing ELLS in order to signify a large range of Englishes and cultures in the works they decide. on the other hand, Achebe's models are all male. It is significance to add two propositions of female authors whose works is productively used in the derivative ESL classes. Chimamanda Adichie conceivably now superior recognized for her "single story" sermon, her first novel, *Purple Hibiscus*, is an outstanding model of a particularly Nigerian English Literature. It's also an enormous story dealing with subjects matter of religion, domestic mistreatment, and increasing out of domination. This is more suitable for high school students. Beverly Naidoo - South African author of *Journey to Jo'burg* and *The Other Side of Truth*. *The Other Side of Truth* is particularly good for studying as a class novel. The language is fairly simple and appropriate for intermediate middle school students, but the themes are stimulating enough for high school readers as well. As the title implies, one of the main themes is the importance of truth, but it also deals with the refugee experience as it follows the plight of two Nigerian children alone in London.

Conclusion

Achebe illustrates an ending by referring to the effort of James Baldwin. He draws a comparison between this work and his personal thoughts by shaping his appreciation that Baldwin's difficulty is not his, but he feels that the English language will be capable

to hold the influence of his African skill. He also says that it will have to be a new-fangled English, still in full unity with its inherited home but changed to suit its new African background.

Until these authors recognize the fact that exact African literature should be written in African languages, they would be simply practicing a lifeless end, which can only guide to infertility, hesitation, and disturbance, but Achebe thought that one cannot study African literature in a diminutive, efficient definition. African literature is not one component but a connected units in reality, the amount full of all the public and cultural literatures of Africa.

References

Achebe, Chinua, *The African writer and the English Language*, *Transition*, 4, 18, 1965, 27-30.